

Open Schooling: Overcoming barriers from policy to practice.

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Tony Sherborne, Alexandra Okada, Gemma Young
tonysherborne@gmail.com;
ale.okada@open.ac.uk; younggemma123@gmail.com

Abstract. The UK's CONNECT project aimed to create high-quality teaching resources aligned with school curriculum objectives, promoting Open Schooling in mainstream education. While these resources found favor among teachers, persuading school leaders to embrace this approach presented challenges, given the relatively limited awareness of Open Schooling outside of academic circles. Our research, involving 172 teachers, employed a blend of qualitative and quantitative methods, including interviews, observations, and online surveys. The results reveal increased socio-scientific and emotional engagement among 972 out of 4,300 students, with 82% of students acknowledging the importance of science and math for problem-solving, underscoring the practical value of science education. Our findings lead to recommendations for a new qualification plan for 14–16-year-olds in the UK and underscore the need for increased research grant opportunities to extend the Open Schooling movement within and beyond Europe by 2030.

1. Introduction

The focus of CONNECT project in the UK has been on developing high quality teaching resources aligned to curriculum goals at a school level. The aim of this is to help operationalise Open Schooling in mainstream schools. However, **despite these resources being very popular (4,038 downloads considering various channels and platforms) and enthusiastic** feedback from the network of teachers we have built, it has been hard to convince school leaders to take a risk on what they see as a luxury in the curriculum.

In the UK open schooling as a pedagogy is not well understood outside of academic circles and small pockets of enthusiasts in individual schools or organisations such as the Green Forum whose aim is to support the UK Government in the DfE Sustainability education action plan [1]. Despite our efforts, the benefits of Open Schooling to wider society are not well understood in the UK - there seems little recognition of the added benefits to the child and to society of empowering our students by helping them connect science to their lives.

2. Transformative effects of Open Schooling

Many schools are not yet interested in open schooling because their focus is on easily memorisable knowledge for exams, or surface learning. You can imagine this as the visible part of an iceberg.

Whereas open schooling aims more at what is beneath the surface of the iceberg: deep understanding which students can apply beyond the classroom, known as transfer (figure 1). This is what students need to be prepared for further studies and interested in STEM careers. Even for non-STEM students, scientific literacy is important to engage with societal issues and think scientifically. In a world with advanced AI, we need individuals who can do more than just surface learning [2]. In CONNECT, science education has bigger goals. We can bring together the different perspectives by viewing learning as a journey from surface learning to deep learning to transfer knowledge [3] for problem solving in real-life.

Our aims were to show UK schools the transformative effects of Open Schooling on both teaching approaches and students' engagement, understanding including science capital and affective engagement [3] in order to encourage schools to adopt Open Schooling strategies going forwards. Our materials unify diverse perspectives by considering learning as a progression from surface learning to deep learning and ultimately to the application of knowledge [4]. In our model, the "KNOW" phase corresponds to surface learning, but certain CONNECT Science activities are designed to deepen this learning. On the other hand, the "DO" phase focuses on transferring knowledge and skills to new contexts. The social context introduced in the "CARE" component is also a crucial factor in facilitating students' ability to apply knowledge from the classroom to real-world situations. Therefore, CONNECT encourages interaction with families to link science to real-life concerns and with scientists to provide authentic examples of scientific thinking, thereby building students' confidence in applying science in their daily lives. The three components of the CARE-KNOW-DO framework mutually support each other to enhance students' engagement with science, making them equally indispensable for long-term sustainability.

Figure 1: Open Schooling helps students to obtain deep transferable learning (Sherborne, 2023)

3. Methodology

In order to break down some of the barriers to adopting Open Schooling we designed a number of high-quality open schooling resources underpinned by the CARE-KNOW-DO framework for students to develop science-actions (table 1). These materials are simple to implement, are based on engaging socio-scientific topics, have strong links to the UK science curriculum and vary in length, making them suitable to be used in a wide variety of classrooms. The science-actions were free to download both from the CONNECT and Mastery Science website and were advertised by means of newsletters and social media posts.

Table 1: Science actions created for the CONNECT project

Name	Curriculum area	Science actions for students do towards real-life socio-scientific issues' solutions
Rewilding	Food webs, competition	Persuade the public that an extinct animal should be rewilded back into UK forests.
Energy savers	Energy transfer, energy efficiency	Create a funding campaign for a new energy saving home device.
Carbon neutral	Climate change	Act as carbon consultants to help a café become carbon neutral.
Poo transplants	Digestion	Help a friend decide whether to have a faecal transplant.
Microplastics	Particle model, mixtures	Design an invention to stop microplastic pollution of the oceans.

Qualitative methods such as interviews and observations provided in-depth perspectives, while quantitative methods, using online surveys for both teachers and students were supported by the CONNECT-science instrument. These measured how many open-schooling strategies teachers used and their confidence. In students we looked at and measured science capital and affective engagement [5].

4. Transformation in UK teachers

A total of 172 teachers completed the survey. They taught students from year 5 (10-11 years old) to year 13 (17-18) and the majority were female (70%). The experience was positive with 98% of teachers saying they would like to participate in new activities similar to the science-action.

After using a CONNECT science-action, teachers were asked to state which strategies they used normally in their classrooms. Those that were used the most often included:

- Teacher explaining ideas (82% very often or always)
- Teacher demonstrations (61%)
- Students participating in whole class discussion (63%)

These results are evidence that teachers are using didactic teaching methods, an approach that Open Schooling aims to move away from. However, the data does not show what proportion of a lesson is taking up using these approaches so they could feature lightly. Whole class discussions were a popular activity, however small group discussion featured much less frequently (48%). This could reflect a lack of activities where small group discussion is useful, or a lack of confidence in running them, either because of a lack of student or teacher skills.

Strategies that were used the least often were:

- Students using collaborative games/role play (12%)
- Students using textbooks (16%)
- Students developing collaborative inquiry projects (18%)
- Students raising issues for discussion about the topic (29%)

A lack of textbook use in UK schools could be because of a move towards students using other sources of information such as digital resources, budgetary constraints or students not being able to access them. As one teacher explained in a comment: *“support for literacy and numeracy is vitally important as well as digital competency”*. Using collaborative approaches is a feature of Open Schooling that UK teachers use the least. This is most likely because of a lack of training into how to

use them. One comment from a teacher supports this hypothesis “*project work is an issue - I don't know how to do it but am expected to*”. A lack of time in the curriculum is also a likely explanation.

Teachers were also asked to rate how confident they were with Open Schooling activities. They rated the highest confidence in:

- Teaching scientific enquiry with real life problems (71% confident for the most parts or very confident)
- Promoting science learning activities beyond the school curriculum (67%)
- Promoting discussion about science in society in the classroom (62%)
- Helping students to air their views and listen carefully to others in group discussions (62%)

These were aspects that featured most prominently in the science-actions, which showed that the resources helped teachers to develop these aspects of Open Schooling. This is encouraging, and the hope is that teachers will continue to use these.

Lowest levels of confidence were seen in:

- Using questions to trigger divergent modes of thinking and argumentation (34%)
- Encouraging students to discuss science topics with family members (40%)
- Discussing with students the learning goals that include scientists (41%)
- Help students generate questions with evidence-based views (52%)

These point to areas that could be developed in future projects.

Around half of teachers (45%) reported that families participated in the activities, with varying success. One teacher commented that “*families discussed the various options for rewilding. This was a successful homework*”, while another reported that 'some parents did not want to/appropriately take part but a lot did'. The success of family involvement relies on good school/parent relationships and historical experience of parental involvement in home activities, which varies from school to school.

The majority of schools (59%) did have scientists participating in the activities, using either videos, online meetings or in person. The scientists carried out a variety of roles including discussing technologies and judging student presentations. One teacher commented “*we felt a lot more confident in having experts work with us*”.

5. Transformation in UK students

Approximately 4,300 underserved students engaged in a science-driven initiative under the guidance of 172 teachers. On average, each teacher had a classroom with 25 students, consistent with the typical classroom size in the UK. Out of this entire cohort, 910 students (equivalent to 21%) voluntarily participated in the CONNECT-SCIENCE questionnaire. Many of these students attended state schools (84%) that offered free meals. After completing a science-action, the majority of students agreed that learning science will be useful in their daily lives and science helps people (64%). They also saw the importance in maths and science for solving problems (82%).

Qualitative data indicated various benefits for young learners with the CARE- KNOW-DO resources, for example, using their intrinsic motivation to explore and expand their knowledge. One student aged 12 commented “*what I learned with connect science project is to delve deeper into things that interest me and always have the motivation to learn*”. This indicates students connect with science if it is based on something they are interested in. This is a key approach for the CARE phase by which students create questions, discuss issues, present ideas and map their views about socio-scientific issues that they care about.

In the KNOW stage, students expressed their enjoyment and interest in expanding their knowledge by discovering new things. One student aged 13 told us they think science is important “*To find out things which I didn't know before*”.

In the DO phase, various students indicated that they like to take action and learning by doing, as shown by a student aged 14 “*I like projects and creating things in science, we work in groups, working with other people was fun*”.

Just under half of students feel confident with their knowledge in science and in using science to come up with questions and ideas (48%). Most students felt confident doing science projects (67%) but

only half felt able to talk about science (50%) and how to justify their views using arguments and evidence (49%).

However, around 30% of students in each case were unsure. This highlights the fact that with further intervention, these students could be helped to become more confident.

In terms of the importance of science in their lives, very few did science activities outside of school, with 77% reporting 'never or rarely'. This points to UK students having a low science capital, further supported to the fact that even though 62% of students felt that 'science is fun' (and 97% said they would like to do more activities like these) only 26% would like a job that uses science. This shows that even though the majority of students in the UK enjoy science, a minority will likely pursue science into higher education and beyond. Further work could be done on persuading students to pursue a scientific career.

Nearly half of students (49%) know someone working with science. As only 26% have parents who work in science, this highlights the positive impact the project had on their interaction with scientists. As one student commented: 'I learned from scientists that science can be enjoyable and fun.'

The following images show student work from the Energy Savers science action (figure 2 and figure 3)

Figure 2: A decision tree used by a student to decide whether they would buy a charger powered by a hot drink.

Figure 3: A fundraising campaign to raise funds to develop their chosen device – a solar powered cap.

Figure 3 was completed by a student aged 12. They added facts and opinions to the decision tree to help organise their thoughts. Using their knowledge of energy transfer, they correctly identified a flaw in the device, 'it works when the drink is hotter than the room, the drink will cool down so it will stop working'. Because of this, they decided that they would not buy the device.

6. Conclusions

We have had great success with a significant number of teachers in UK but it has proved hard to scale up adoption of Open Schooling approaches in the UK. There are various significant barriers e.g. lack of teaching time, the pressure put on teachers from leadership to focus on exam success, risk aversion to anything new and not well understood by school leadership. Interventions at a school curriculum level like this have not been enough to produce sustainable change at scale. We also know from other work in the last few decades that interventions at a national level e.g., to the national curriculum are very difficult to achieve due to access to important stakeholders and a constantly changing policy environment.

One strategy that we are now pursuing is moving from only production of resources to the whole qualification. In the UK we are developing a concept of a "Science in practice" 14-16 qualification, which will sit alongside the traditional knowledge-based science course and aims to prepare students to make sense of and actively participate in contemporary science issues, through study of the nature of science and experience of carrying out enquiries. We are gaining support from teachers, scientists, and professional bodies. We also emphasize the crucial need for additional research grants to solidify the substantial work accomplished not only within CONNECT but also in all European Union-funded projects. This will contribute to strengthening and expanding the Open Schooling movement, with a significant impact toward achieving EU Missions and Agenda 2030 by 2030.

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